

The Impact of Work Life Quality on Job Burnout (A Field Study on the Petroleum Sector Companies in the Arab Republic of Egypt)

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Abstract:- The current study aimed at assessing the impact of quality of work life practices on the job burnout of workers in petroleum sector companies in the Arab Republic of Egypt, through the mediating role test to empower workers. By analyzing the questionnaire data that was obtained from a soft sample of (277) individuals from the study sample and to review the results of the study that were obtained. In the following, the researcher analyzed the data that had been obtained from 277 employees at various administrative levels. To analyze the obtained data 28 SPSS and AMOS2 6.have been used, it is one of the popular statistical software. Through this program, a descriptive analysis of the demographic characteristics of the sample was obtained, in addition to testing the study hypotheses, where the following results were reached:

The work life quality practices are applied in the organization under study to a medium degree, and the highest dimensions applied were supervisory behavior, job characteristics and physical work environment conditions, and the least applied were compensation and benefits.

The presence of the variable of job burnout in the organization under study in a medium degree, and the highest axes were present with a high degree of low personal achievement, and the least presence of them was dulling of feelings.

- Regarding the employee empowerment variable, it was found that it is applied to a moderate degree. The results of the study hypotheses test also concluded that:

The presence of a significant effect with a statistically significant reverse of the practices of the quality of work life on the job burnout of workers. We find that the most influential dimensions of quality of work life are supervisory behaviour, progress and promotion, and the least influential are after occupational traits. Administrative empowerment mediates the relationship between quality-of-life practices and partial job burnout.

Keywords:- quality of work life, job burnout, administrative empowerment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary organizations face an unprecedented set of technological, political, economic, social challenges, limited resources, and intensified competition internationally, regionally and locally, these challenges forced many organizations around the world to make fundamental transformations in order to maintain continuity.

There is no doubt that the human element is one of the most important assets in the organization, as it is the strategic and basic resource for it, as the extent of its success or failure depends on the use of this resource, which ensures the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage, and the researchers agreed that financial resources were the most important factor for the success of institutions, except This philosophy no longer exists today, as employee quality of life, job satisfaction and ethics have become the most serious determinants of the stability and excellence of organizations. (Obeidat and Rawabdhah, 2020)

The issue of the quality of the functional life of workers has captured the attention of researchers and practitioners alike in the field of organizational behavior in Western countries, but the interest in this subject has not reached the acceptable degree in developing countries, where many studies have recently been concerned with measuring the quality of career life under the dimensions of Various and new deep challenges by stimulating the creative energies of individuals, enhancing competitiveness, employee commitment and participation in achieving organizational goals. (Al-Biyari and Abu Muammar ,2018)

The interest in the quality of career life also began in the early seventies, and there were many studies and research that dealt with many aspects of the quality of working life, and departments in many large institutions started comprehensive and integrated projects, to improve productivity and work force by studying the organizational effects on the quality of work life, despite the presence of Some concerns, and concerns about some of the things that must be achieved by the various administrative leaders, such as respectable wages, working hours and conditions, promotions, retirement systems, fatigue problems, and control. (Younes and Shaldan, 2017)

Quality of work life means good working conditions, good supervision, salaries, benefits, good rewards and a degree of interest and challenge in the job. Effective at the enterprise level.

The Corporation seeks to improve the various aspects affecting the career life of the employees, and their personal lives as well, and in turn contributes to achieving the strategic objectives of the Corporation, its employees and those who deal with it.

As it represents each of the following elements: fair wages and compensation, healthy and safe working conditions, and available opportunities for the development and development of human capabilities, future opportunities for job growth and job security, constitutional rights for employees of the institution, social integration in the work of the institution, balance between the career and personal life of employees and the moral and social responsibility of the organization. (Aysha, 2012)

The phenomenon of (job burnout), which if it appears in any organization, leads to failure, and loss of energy as a result of lack of interest in the human resource within the organization and the inability of workers to deal with the sources that generate pressures (Boyed, 2011). Where it is the fate that all businesses try to avoid.

From this point of view, this research sought to study the influence relationship of quality of work life practices on job combustion through the mediating effect of administrative empowerment by applying it to workers in petroleum sector companies in the Arab Republic of Egypt.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT:

The concept of the quality of functional life is one of the modern concepts in business organizations, especially in the field of human resource management (Diob 2014). about them, or a reduction in the services and social benefits provided to them, or a reduction in their wage rates, in addition to the keenness of these organizations to achieve job satisfaction that affects the commitment of workers, and then maximizing the importance of using and rationalizing the performance of human resources, and considering it one of the effective strategies in strengthening competitive excellence For Business Organizations (Gad Al-Rub, 2003)

Many studies have dealt with the concept of quality of functional life as follows, where (Khosrowp, 2001) defined it in the fact that the quality of functional life is achieved by fulfilling human requirements at work (good working conditions, good supervision, healthy climate, good relationships, salaries and rewards) and added (Maghrebi, 2004) that the quality of career is achieved through the philosophy that the organization adopts in the relationship between employees to give them the opportunity to influence their jobs and effectively contribute at the level of the organization.

Also (Al-Desouki and Abdel Salam, 2015) agreed with (Alexandra.T, 2017) about addressing the quality of work life as a means to provide or meet the personal needs of employees, then added (Desouky and Abdel Salam, 2015) that it contributes to raising the level of performance efficiency. organizations that affect the career life of employees as well.

He also added (Indumathy & Kamalraj, 2012) that it is a new angle for the concept of quality of work life based on considering the employees as one of the assets of the organization instead of considering them as a cost to it, and I suppose that the performance of employees is better when they are allowed to manage their work themselves, and agreed with (Al-Maghrabi, 2004) Assuming to contribute to decision-making, as it motivates workers to meet their needs.

In a more comprehensive view, (Jad Al-Rub, 2008) defined the quality of career as the integrated, planned and continuous processes, which aim to improve the various aspects that affect the career and personal lives of employees, which in turn contributes to achieving the strategic goals of the organization and its employees. Those who deal with it, and with this comprehensive view, agreed with him (Madi, 2014) in addressing the quality of career life as a set of systems and programs related to the improvement and development of the human capital of the organization, which would affect the career life of individuals and Their social environment, which in turn contributes to achieving the goals of the organization and all parties related to the organization.

(Surya, 2012) also dealt with the quality of work life in a different way, where he defined it as the degree of excellence that is created in the work, and the work conditions that determine the relationship between the worker and his environment, in addition to the human dimension, which contributes in its entirety to general satisfaction and improving capabilities in work performance. On the individual level, and then on the level of performance of the organization as a whole, as agreed with (Madi, 2014) in the fact that a good work environment is concerned with providing ingredients that improve the level of job performance for employees, and he agreed with (Al-Salem, 2009) in Addressing the quality of career life in the degree of excellence that is in the work environment, by creating trends and positive aspects in them that employees or individuals within the organization realize.

Through the foregoing, the researcher agrees with the definition set by (Jad Al-Rub, 2008), where he defined the quality of career as the planned and continuous complementary processes, which aim to improve the various aspects that affect the career and personal lives of employees, which in turn contributes to In achieving the strategic objectives of the organization, its employees and those who deal with it.

Through the researcher's approach to the concept of quality of work life, the following points can be suggested:

A concept based on several things such as providing human needs at work, the degree of harmony between work tasks and health and social needs, salaries, good rewards, and other things that must be available in the work environment.

The application of the concept of quality of functional life aims to create a good work environment that raises the efficiency of performance in organizations, which in turn

leads to the achievement of the strategic objectives of the organization.

The benefits achieved by the concept of quality of functional life are that it works to increase the profitability and efficiency of the organization, satisfy the needs of the workers and raise the level of their satisfaction with the organization, which pushes the workers within the organization to exert the maximum possible energy, which leads to raising the efficiency of the organization and achieving its goals.

Despite the relative recentness of the phenomenon of job burnout, as there are many studies that describe and categorize it in multiple ways, which led to the emergence of various definitions of job burnout characterized by disagreement on its concept. (Al-Kalabi and Rashid, 2001) Here are the most prominent definitions that came with it:

- (Maslak) defines job burnout as a state of psychological, emotional and mental stress, which appears in the form of severe fatigue, a sense of uselessness, loss of hope, and the development of a concept with a negative orientation and negative attitudes towards work and people (Al Jamali and Hassan, 2003).
- Maslak believes that psychological burnout affects professionals who face obstacles that prevent them from performing the required role, which may lead to a feeling of helplessness and failure to perform the work at the expected level, and it is the result of a low level of defensiveness and a feeling of dissatisfaction and loss of interest in those who receive services such as students And the sick and others (Al Farah, 2001)
- The researchers (Ozturk, 2020, 2020) developed a procedural definition of combustion based on the literature and research that dealt with it and stipulated the following: "Occupational combustion is the response to emotional stress caused by psychological stress, low performance at work, and a dry style of dealing with others.
- It was also defined as a state of emotional, intellectual, and physical exhaustion, which is in the form of expressions that the individual uses towards a currency as responses to stress and chronic organizational relationships. This case includes the individual's sense that emotional confiscation is exhausting and tends to negatively evaluate himself and a feeling of low The level of his efficiency at work and the loss of his personal commitment in work relations, in addition to the loss of the human element in dealing with others inside and outside the organization (Al-Kalabi and Rashid, 2001)
- Burnout was defined by Maslash and Jackson as a lack of energy and emotions at work (Omar & Nasurdin, 2020), especially among workers in professions that have a direct relationship with the beneficiaries of their services.
- (Galiana et al., 2021) has described burn-out as a psychological syndrome, whereby workers feel that they are emotionally drained and depersonalized, with a feeling of low level of personal achievement.

Despite the different definitions of functional combustion, there are points on which most of the different points of view agree, and they are that functional combustion:

- It happens on an individual level
- It is an internal negative psychological experience that includes feelings, attitudes, motives, and expectations
- It includes a negative change in the response to others, as it includes a negative or inappropriate response to change
- It includes a negative response to the self and its concept (Al Jamali and Hassan, 2003)

The importance of empowerment stems from the fact that it focuses on the human element, which is the basis for success in business organizations (Al-Wadi, 2012). There is no doubt that trying to identify this concept and its impact on workers is an important factor in determining the factors that influence and motivate them to perform their work in a better way than In the end, it affects them and the organization.

Hence the importance of administrative empowerment as a modern administrative concept that aims to exploit the available human energy, move away from complexity and facilitate the task of employees in performing their work, and create job creativity.

And (Al-Fayyadh, 2005) believes that administrative empowerment contributed to raising the morale of employees and enhancing organizational loyalty to achieve their goals and the goals of the organization, in addition to that, administrative empowerment expresses the culture of the organization. In other than leadership levels, in addition to freedom of action and responsibility (Al-Assaf, 2006)

A. *The importance of the study stems from the fact that:*

Most of the previous studies that dealt with the quality of job life focused on measuring the impact of the quality of job life on several variables such as: organizational commitment (Al-Ruwati, 2017), job burnout (Al-Barbari, 2016), organizational effectiveness (Al-Hashimi and Al-Adayleh, 2018), but it was few.

Also, most of the previous studies focused on the government sector, education, and banking. Regarding the previous studies that dealt with the relationship between quality of work life and job burnout, they were few to the researcher's knowledge. The scarcity of studies, to the researcher's knowledge, that dealt with the quality of career, as most of the studies have been applied in other Arab countries. The lack of studies that dealt with the quality of work life and empowerment of workers

So, the following model testing the impact of work life balance practices on the job burnout through investigating the mediation effect of employee empowerment.

quantitative companies in

A number of (357) forms were distributed, and a number of (301) forms were returned, and (277) forms were analyzed.

For the purpose of this study, a questionnaire has been adopted from previous studies. The questionnaire was closed-ended questions and respondents were asked to rank their agreement with the statements indicated through 5-Likert scale to measure the Study variables.

The Research Conceptual Framework
To answer the research objectives, the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) was used.

First, the reliability of the constructs was tested using Cronbach's alpha. The results showed that the Cronbach's alpha values for all constructs were higher than the cut-off value (> 0.50). This indicates convergent validity of all constructs of the study.

IV. RESULTS

The first main hypothesis: “there is a statistically significant effect work life balance on job burnout” and the sub-hypotheses include:

1th sub-hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of compensation and benefits on job burnout.

variable	B	std. Error standard error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	2.975	0.202		14.725	0
Compensation and benefits	0.66-	0.439	0.044	-11.379	0
R ²	0.476				

*At significance level α <=0.01

Table 1: The regression analysis of compensation & benefits effect on Job burnout

As noted from the statistical results presented in Table (1), and from the follow-up to the values of the (t) test that the compensation and benefits dimension has an adverse effect on the job burnout, as the calculated (T) values amounted to -11.379, which are significant values at the level of significance (It was also found that the

compensation and benefits dimension predicts about 47.6 % as an impact factor of changes in the level of job burnout among employees, which proves the validity and acceptance of the first sub-hypothesis.

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation:

Job burnout = 2.975-0.66 compensation and benefits

2nd sub-hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of promotion and advancement dimension on job burnout

variable	B	std. Error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	3.084	0.15		20,543	0
promotion and advancement	-.012-	0.049	-.028-	-.245-	0.04
R ²	0.63				
*At significance level $\alpha \leq 0.01$					

Table 2: The regression analysis of promotion and advancement effect on Job burnout

As it is clear from the statistical results presented in Table (2) , and from the follow-up to the values of the (t) test that after promotion and advancement have an adverse effect on job burnout, the calculated (T) values amounted to -.249), which are significant values at the level of significance ($0.005 \geq \alpha$), and also found that after promotion and advancement, it predicts about 63% as an impact factor of changes in the level of job burnout among employees, which proves the validity and acceptance of the second sub-hypothesis.

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation:

Job burnout = 3.084-0.12 promotion and advancement

3rd sub-hypothesis: There is a significant effect of statistical significance for the dimension of the balance between life and work on job burnout.

variable	B	std. Error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	3.267	0.217		15	0
Balance between life and work	-.067-	0.065	-.118-	-21.028	0.03
R ²	0.53				
*At the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$					

Table 3: The regression analysis of Balance between life and work effect on Job burnout

As it is clear from the statistical results presented in Table (3) , and from the follow-up to the values of the (t) test, that after the balance between life and work has an adverse effect on job burnout, where the calculated (t) values amounted to -21,028, which are significant values at the level of Significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$), as it was found that the life-work balance dimension predicts about 53% as an impact factor of changes in the level of job burnout among

employees, which proves the validity and acceptance of the third sub-hypothesis.

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation

Job burnout = 3.267-.067 Work- life balance

4th sub-hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of the job attributes dimension on job burnout.

variable	B	std. Error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	2.975	0.209		14,243	0
Job Attributes	0.782895-	0.055	0.043	9.369-	0.013
R ²	0.23				
*At the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$					

Table 4: The regression analysis of Job attributes and work effect on Job burnout

As it is clear from the statistical results presented in Table (4) , and from the follow-up of the values of the (t) test that the dimension of the job attributes has an adverse effect on the job burnout, where the calculated (T) values reached -9.369), which are significant values at the level of significance (It was also found that the job attributes

dimension predicts about 23% as an effect factor of changes in the level of job burnout among employees, which proves the validity and acceptance of the fourth sub-hypothesis.

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation:

Job burnout = 2.975 - 0.782895 job attributes

5th sub-hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect of the supervisory behavior dimension on job burnout.

variable	B	std. Error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	3.132	0.186		16,857	0
supervisory behavior	-0.152.923	0.05	.053-	-22.46	0.047
Total Impact Factor R ²	0.73				
*At the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$					

Table 5: The regression analysis of supervisory behavior effect on Job burnout

As it is clear from the statistical results presented in Table (5-26), and from the follow-up of the values of the (t) test that the supervisory behavior dimension has an adverse effect on the job burnout, where the calculated (T) values amounted to -22.46), which are significant values at the level of significance (It also found that the supervisory behavior dimension predicts about 73% as an effect factor of changes in the level of job burnout among employees, which

proves the validity and acceptance of the fifth sub-hypothesis.

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation:

$$\text{Job burnout} = 3.132 - 0.152.923 \text{ Supervisory behavior}$$

6th sub-hypothesis: There is a significant, statistically significant effect of the dimension of physical work conditions on job burnout.

variable	B	std. Error	β	value (t)	P-value
(Constant)	3.585	0.219		16,351	0
physical working conditions	-.141-	0.056	-.278-	-2.508-	0.014
R ²	0.42				
*At the significance level $\alpha \leq 0.05$					

Table 6: The regression analysis of physical working conditions effect on Job burnout

It is also evident from the statistical results presented in Table (6) , and from the follow-up to the values of the (t) test that after the physical work conditions has an adverse effect on the job burnout, where the calculated (t) values amounted to -2.508, which are significant values at the level of Significance ($\alpha \geq 0.05$), as it was found that the dimension of the work environment predicts about 42% as an impact factor of changes in the level of job burnout among employees, which proves the validity and acceptance of the sixth sub-hypothesis

The regression effect can also be represented by the following equation:

$$\text{Occupational burnout} = 3.585 - .141 \text{ physical working conditions}$$

The second main hypothesis: employee empowerment mediates the relationship between quality of work life and job burnout

trace	Variables	quality of work life		
direct effect	Empowering workers	0.792	0.875	0.01
	Job burnout	0.06	0.32	0.005
indirect effect	Empowering workers	0	0	...
	Job burnout	0.005	0.86	0.051

Table 7: The Mediation analysis of employee empowerment on the relationship between work life balance and Job burnout

It is noted from Table (7) that the results of conducting a median effect test analysis using AMOS26 , that there is a direct impact on the quality of job life on job burnout (CI:95%P-value:0.005,UCI:0.32,LCI:0.06) , as He found an indirect quality effect life functional On combustion Employment through the mediating effect of employee empowerment (P-value: 0.051, UCI:0.86,LCI:0.005), meaning that employee empowerment mediates the relationship between the quality of job life on job burnout in partially , which leads to partially accepting the second hypothesis

V. DISCUSSION

The results analysis indicates - The presence of significant reverse of the practices of the quality of work life on the job burnout of workers. We find that the most influential dimensions of quality of work life are supervisory behavior, progress and promotion, and the least influential are after occupational traits.

Administrative empowerment mediates the relationship between quality-of-life practices and partial job burnout.

Scientific contribution: In this research, the researcher took into consideration the academic meaning, as the research discusses the impact of the quality of career life on the level of job burnout for workers, so work must be done to develop the research model with other factors that can affect this relationship through future research.

Practical contribution: The results of the study have many implications for decision-makers. Therefore, decision makers should focus on increasing attention to the quality of work life practices of employees, to work on enhancing employee empowerment.

The research aims to study the extent of the impact of the quality of career life on job burnout among workers through the mediating effect of empowering workers. The results of the research showed some recommendations to practitioners in the field:

- Giving institutions greater attention to the elements of quality of job life that affect other organizational factors such as job burnout, job satisfaction and performance.
- To reduce the level of job burnout, employees must be encouraged to reveal the negatives they face at work. By building multiple communication channels and following the open-door policy.
- Diversify job tasks to reduce work routine Rotate jobs to reduce boredom and boredom
- Creating an organizational climate in which human relations are strengthened. Creating a good atmosphere in which the spirit of participation and cooperation prevails
- Supporting human relations between management and workers, exchanging enrichment and viewpoints on work problems through continuous meetings
- Clarity of the role of each of them to form teams for job tasks by raising the degree of enthusiasm for work

This research contains many recommendations that may be useful for future research:

- Future research can look at conducting the study in other service sectors (such as: education, tourism, health), and therefore for the ease of generalizing the results of the study.
- Carrying out comparative studies on the elements of the quality of functional life between the different administrative levels: senior, middle and direct management.

This research has many limitations through the study it dealt with, as the first limitation is that despite the fact that the researcher collected data from one company in Alexandria Governorate. In addition, the second limitation of this research is the time limit to finish the research, which was an obstacle to collecting a larger sample size to represent the data under study. The third restriction was the period in which the research was conducted and the variables in it, such as the Corona virus and the economic crises resulting from this epidemic.

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